

Community Strength Creation in Accordance with Thailand 4.0

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 30, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Strength of community, The age of Thailand 4.0, Khon Kaen Province, Thailand</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4783567</p>	<p><i>This research aims to study the strength of community, study the method of fortifying strength to community, and propose the guideline for building strength to the community in Nong-Krunghthanasan Sub-District Administrative Organization (NSAO), Phu-Wiang District, Khon Kaen Province in the age of Thailand 4.0. This study is qualitative research utilizing an In-Depth Interview and Focus Group Discussion with 60 key respondents. The research was analyzed by description analysis following the inductive method. The results of the research were as follows: 1) there are six categories of the strength of community: 1) the quality of life, 2) community-economics-having innovation of community-knowledge, 3) social network, 4) safety in life and properties-having village-volunteers, 5) management of natural resources and environment, and 6) community culture-keeping on local culture, enabling it to the peacefulness of community; 2) there are five methods of fortifying strength to the community: 1) public relations, and knowledge-sharing 2) meeting, 3) public hearing of community, 4) preparing plan, and 5) following up and evaluation; 3) there are five guidelines for building the strength of the community in terms of 1) technology, 2) economics, 3) resources, 4) management, and 5) network. These five guidelines would enable the community to affluence, stability, and sustainability.</i></p>

Introduction

In the past, there were three development models of Thailand. Thailand 1.0 focused on agriculture, such as horticulture, hog, and chicken production and sale. Thailand 2.0 emphasized the light industry, such as the manufacture and sale of footwear, leather goods, beverages, jewelry, stationery, bags, and apparel. Thailand 3.0 emphasized advanced industries for economic growth, such as steel, automobile, natural gas, and cement. Today, Thailand 4.0 is the economic model to unlock the economic challenges from the past three models: a middle-income trap, an inequality trap, and an imbalanced trap (Washington D.C. Royal Thai Embassy, 2021)(Jones & Pimdee, 2017).

The world situation today is changing faster and more complex. The impacts coming from the 4th Industrial Revolution or Industry 4.0 have brought changes in all dimensions, including business, investment, and the way of life. Therefore, adapting to meet the changes is a challenge faced by many countries worldwide, including Thailand (Office of the Spokesperson, 2017). In response to such challenges, the promotion of the Thailand 4.0 policy has been used to create the country's competitiveness. The critical factor in coping with this global trend is the human capital's readiness (Office of the Spokesperson, 2017). According to the National Strategy, building 'the community strength' is one way to create such readiness. It aims to develop and strengthen human capital to improve Thai people of all ages in a multi-dimensional manner to become good, skillful, and quality citizens (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2020). However, based on human capital management, community strength building is generally different based on social conditions and the community's social cost and potential.

As the Eleventh National Economic and Social Development Plan is still defective, the government must change the plan to suit global situations with clear directions and objectives. The government now encourages every social sector to participate in the national development to pursue its goals 'A Secure Nation, Contented People, Continued Economic Growth, An Equal Society and Sustainable Natural Resources' (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2020). Therefore, researchers are interested in conducting research on building strength in the community, emphasizing studying the ways and methods to overcome the traps of middle income, inequality, and imbalance in the northeast region of the country. In so doing, the researchers have conducted the research in collaboration with the Nong-Krunghthanasan Subdistrict

Administrative Organization (NSAO) in Phu Wiang District, Khon Kean Province, to find the ways for creating strength for the communities under its administrative region.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study was carried out utilizing the qualitative research methodology with the following objectives: 1) to study the community strength under NSAO, Phu Wiang District, Khon Kaen Province; 2) to study the process of strength building for the community under NSAO; 3) to propose the methods of strength community building in Thailand 4.0 for communities under NSAO.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This research was qualitative research using cooperatively Participatory Action Research (PAR) for building the community strength. The researchers specified five aspects of the conceptual framework as follows:

Document: primary sources included Thai Tipitaka, the Twelfth National Economic and Social Development Plan, and In-depth-interview data; secondary sources included academic works, books, textbooks, articles, and related research about the strength enhancement for the community in Thailand 4.0.

Contexts: the contexts of study involved: community strength, the process of community strength building, and the method of strength community building in Thailand 4.0 with five aspects: T (technology), E (economy), R (resource), M (management), S (social network).

Area: the researchers chose NSAO in Phu Wiang District, Khon Kaen Province, as a research area because of its reputation as a strong community with strength building based on the vision in Thailand 4.0.

Key Informants: 60 key informants were chosen from one community based on the consideration of their rewards for strength-building for their communities. They were monks, local administrative organization staff, community leaders, community developers, educational administrators, volunteers, and youth leaders.

Research Duration: March - September 2020.

RESULTS

1) The community strength of NSAO comprised of six aspects: (1) life quality through activity and project; such as senior citizens school, festival celebration, (2) community economy; local wisdom innovations, (3) networking; cooperating with other communities, (4) life and asset security; community volunteers, (5) natural resources and environment management; established the disaster watch center for natural resources and environment, (6) community culture; followed local traditions for a peaceful community.

2) The process of strength building for the community of NSAO consisted of five processes: (1) public relations and knowledge sharing, (2) meeting, (3) public participation, (4) planning, (5) follow-up and evaluation. These aspects are important for community strength with stability, affluence, and sustainability.

3) The ways of strong community building in Thailand 4.0 for communities NSAO, Khon Kaen Province consisted of five aspects: (1) community technology: people relied on self-reliance for community benefit, (2) community economy: it was the foundation of local wisdom, and community culture cost with enough income, (3) community resources: it was community cost with plentiful natural resources by nature and artificial, (4) community management: it was to manage local wisdom by community organization and people life-long learning, (5) community networking: four occupational groups including handicraft, agriculture, therapeutic massage, processed food; wisdom group; information group.

V. DISCUSSION

The study revealed many interesting issues. First, community strength was created by the following aspects: 1) life quality, 2) community economy, 3) community networking, 4) life and asset security, 5) natural resources and environment management, and 6) community culture. This conformed to the study by Atchara Sarobol (Atchara Sarobol, 2008) stated in 'Community and Development' that the development is multi-changing processes of society, such as economy, politics, education, religion, family, relatives, technological science, norm, value, and regulation. The significant development is used as the country development method enhanced people to rely on self-reliance with the adaptations of resources and environment according to the influence of negotiations of economy, society and politics of external communities, and life and asset security, it relates to the study 'Development of Strong Community: A Case Study of Poonbumpen Community, Phase Charoen District, Bangkok'(Kamonsak Wongsrikeaw, 2016). Its result found that the Poonbumpen Community's characteristics reflected self-reliance competencies, community security, community vision, and community cherishing. The factors that fostered a strong community were closed social relationships, learning for improving people's lives, community network, natural leader, and economy of self-reliance. Furthermore, the suggestions for developing a sustainable strength of the community were to continue farmland preservation, promote newcomers the awareness, create an ongoing community development activity, implement proactive community public relations, and create the leaders of a new generation for mission networking.

The process of strength building for the community of NSAO, Phu Wiang District, Khon Kaen Province could be concluded that there were five processes: 1) public relations and knowledge sharing, 2) meeting, 3)

people's participation, 4) planning, 5) follow-up and evaluation. These aspects are essential for community strength in Thailand 4.0, related to the community strength study of Somboon Tumlangka (2012) in Chiang Rai Province, indicating that in terms of the social context of strength communities in Chiang Rai province, there was a system of relatives with horizontal and vertical social structures. In a political context, the communities were entrusted to be self-governed. In the cultural context, their traditions, beliefs, and rituals were inherited by their ancestors. In an economic context, the communities had plentiful natural resources as productive capital that cooperatively produced and did marketing. Also, the local wisdom was used to strengthen the community. The factors that affected the community strength were the community learning process, community relationship network, and local wisdom. The strategies used to strengthen the community with the foundation of local wisdom were community management, community cooperation, learning process building, networking, and hometown loving awareness building. As mentioned, it also related to the study of Patcharavadee Treechai (2009) in Prachuap Khirikhan Province. Its findings showed two significant factors: Firstly, the significant factors of revitalization for problems society to become a solid and self-reliant community were: 1) the outstanding leadership with a democratic process; 2) people's participation in teamwork, creating good ones, being intelligent, and being skillful; 3) multi-social cost, such as community harmony, elder respecting, and local wisdom; 4) economic cost with self-reliance, occupational group cooperation for decreasing unemployed and debt. Lastly, the strategy that the leader used to revitalize to be a strong community; indicated that to have the council 59 and community plan based on democracy were essential that harmonized all the people. These helped people build occupational networks and community funds to revitalize the economy and society to become stable self-reliant on the foundation of community revitalization.

The methods of strength community building in Thailand 4.0 for communities in NSAO, Phu Wiang District, Khon Kaen Province consisted of five aspects: 1) community technology, 2) community economy, 3) community resources, 4) community management, and 5) community networking. These aspects would enable the community to affluence, stability, and sustainability. This is consistent with the study of Punnapong Wongnasri (2016) on local administration to drive local innovation in Thailand 4.0, which mentioned four issues: 1) contexts and urban change, 2) contexts creating civil state, 3) technology, and 4) research and local innovation development. Moreover, it related to the study on 'Guidelines of development strategy in Thailand 4.0 OTOP: Case Study of Banraichairach Coffee, Amphoe Bang Saphan Noi, Changwat Prachuap Khiri Khan' (Nawaphon Leelawongsanti, Supharaj Nooha, & Thitiporn Samransart, 2018). Its findings showed that the major problems were the limitation of OTOP needs only in a small community and sub-district. They had little materials and were unskillful. Therefore, the problems were at a middle level so that they could develop the policies based on Thailand 4.0, and the holistic view became at a good level. The aspects they developed were as follows: 1) productivity: used more machines to reduce the number of workers, long-term cost and productive time, 2) marketing: improved products' packaging uniquely and promoted via online media, 3) internal organizational management: studied more about technology skills through Thailand 4.0, 4) finance: fundraised for expanding the business and using in emergency case, and rewarding members systematically and equally, 5) resource management, and 6) innovation and technology. As stated previously, it also related to the study on 'the Development for Strengthened Community Management Corresponding to Sufficiency Economy in the Upper Central Provinces of Thailand' (Jandaeng W. & Adiwattanasit J., 2013). The results were found that 1) Sufficient Economy engendered the quality of community organization, 2) community applied Sufficient Economy in community management, occupation, resource management, and organization development in the community, and 3) the form new discovered, it was to administrate the community with Sufficient Economy. Furthermore, this research demonstrated the new finding was 1) the cooperation of strong community supporting as tripartite: community organization, public organization, and supporting organization; 2) strength support system: knowledge, data, and relations; and 3) methods of strong community building were community revitalization, community adaptation, and community existence.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The outcome, processes, and methods of the study should be applied to create the policies in building a strong community in areas. For improving the body of knowledge gained in this study, future research related to building community strength should be conducted in other communities. The results of such studies should be compared with that of this research.

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